

Low-noise supercontinuum using a 1.85 μm fs pump and a normal dispersion ZBLAN fibre

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Extremely low-noise supercontinuum (SC) can be generated using a polarisation-maintaining (PM) all-normal dispersion fibre and a femtosecond (fs) pump [1]. These low-noise SC sources have enabled applications such as shot-noise-limited SC-based ultra-high-resolution optical coherence tomography [2], and broadband scanning near-field optical microscopy [3] in the near-infrared. The specific requirements needed in the advancement of low-noise SC sources have been made possible by the maturity of silica optical fibre technology and ultrafast erbium (Er) lasers. In this work we have investigated the possibility of extending the low-noise SC into the technologically less mature mid-infrared (MIR) wavelength region.

In order to identify fibres that are PM and have a normal dispersion profile in the MIR, precise dispersion of the ZBLAN fibres was measured using a broadband white light interferometry setup that covers 1.4–4.2 μm . The measured dispersion of the fundamental modes in a $6.7 \times 2.7 \mu\text{m}$ elliptical core ZBLAN fibre is shown in Fig. 1(a). The fibre has normal dispersion in the MIR until 3.75 μm and hence is suitable to generate low-noise SC that can extend into the MIR. A novel low-noise fs source centred at 1.85 μm based on the design in Ref. [4] was developed. This source consists of a thulium-doped amplifier seeded by a part of the SC generated using a 1.55 μm , low-noise, ultrafast Er: fibre laser that had a repetition rate of 40 MHz. The output of the thulium-doped amplifier was compressed to 58 fs, and the output average power was 210 mW. The pulse-to-pulse relative intensity noise (RIN) of the 1.85 μm source was measured to be 0.41% using an electronic spectrum analyser. The light out

Fig. 1: (a) Measured dispersion of the fundamental modes in a $6.7 \times 2.7 \mu\text{m}$ elliptical core ZBLAN fibre. (b) Measured spectra and the RIN out of the $6.7 \times 2.7 \mu\text{m}$ elliptical core ZBLAN fibre.

of the 1.85 μm fs source was coupled into one of the fundamental modes of the $6.7 \times 2.7 \mu\text{m}$ core ZBLAN fibre. The fibre length was 1.55 m, and the coupling efficiency was greater than 50%. The low-noise spectrum spans 1.45–2.35 μm and is shown in Fig. 1(b). The spectrally resolved RIN is shown in Fig. 1(b). The measured RIN is as low as 0.22% at 1.7 μm but increases towards the edges of the spectrum.

The SC bandwidth was limited by the peak power (P_0) available from the source. As the dispersion of the fibre is normal in the MIR, an increase in P_0 of the pump would help further broaden the low-noise SC into the MIR.

Funding. Danmarks Frie Forskningsfond project no. 2031-00009B; VILLUM Fonden (2021 Villum Investigator project no. 00037822: Table-Top Synchrotrons); Innovation Fund Denmark project no. 2105-00039B (HYPER SORT); EU’s Horizon Europe project no. 101058054 (TURBO); Schweizerischer Nationalfonds zur Förderung der Wissenschaftlichen Forschung (TMPFP2_210543, PCEFP2_181222).

References

- [1] A. M. Heidt. “Pulse preserving flat-top supercontinuum generation in all-normal dispersion photonic crystal fibers”. *Journal of the Optical Society of America B* 27.3 (Mar. 2010), pp. 550–559.
- [2] S. Rao D. S., M. Jensen, L. Grüner-Nielsen, J. T. Olsen, P. Heiduschka, B. Kemper, J. Schnekenburger, M. Glud, M. Mogensen, N. M. Israelsen, and O. Bang. “Shot-noise limited, supercontinuum-based optical coherence tomography”. *Light: Science & Applications* 10.1 (June 2021), pp. 1–13.
- [3] K. J. Kaltenecker, S. Rao D. S., M. Rasmussen, H. B. Lassen, E. J. R. Kelleher, E. Krauss, B. Hecht, N. A. Mortensen, L. Grüner-Nielsen, C. Markos, O. Bang, N. Stenger, and P. U. Jepsen. “Near-infrared nanospectroscopy using a low-noise supercontinuum source”. *APL Photonics* 6.6 (June 2021), pp. 066106–1–10.
- [4] A. Rampur, Y. Stepanenko, G. Stępniewski, T. Kardaś, D. Dobrakowski, D.-M. Spangenberg, T. Feurer, A. Heidt, and M. Klimczak. “Ultra low-noise coherent supercontinuum amplification and compression below 100 fs in an all-fiber polarization-maintaining thulium fiber amplifier”. *Optics Express* 27.24 (Nov. 2019), pp. 35041–35051.